

Table 1. Research on Digital Humanities Construction in Foreign Countries

Research Topics	Author	Library	Main research content
Foreign Digital Humanities Service Research	Li Lirui, Wang Boya, 2019	Northwest A&F University Library	Survey of Digital Academic Services of iSchools University Libraries
	Xia Jinjin, 2018	ChangZhi Medical College Library	Columbia University Library Digital Humanities Service Research
	Ma Ning, 2018	East China Normal University Library	Melbourne University Library eScholarship Service Practice Study
	E Lijun, 2018	Yan Shan University Library	Survey of Digital Academic Services in British University Libraries
	Qian Guofu, 2017	Guangdong University of Foreign Studies Library	Digital Humanities Service at Lancaster University Library, UK
	Yu Yaxiu, Li Xin, 2018	East China Normal University Library	Digital Humanities Service Practice at the University of California, Los Angeles Library
	Ma Ning, 2018	East China Normal University Library	Melbourne University Library eScholarship Service Practice Study
	Lu Yan, Lu Zhangping, 2019	Jiangsu University Library	Research on Service Transformation and Development of American University Libraries
Introduction of foreign digital humanities construction and application	Zhang Chen, Wu Yanxi, Dai Ping, 2017	Sichuan University Library	Application Research of Big Data Intelligent Visualization in University Libraries in North America
	Chen Zhou, 2017	Chongqing University of Arts and Sciences Library	Digital Humanities Application Research in European and American Libraries
	Yu Tingting, 2017	Shanghai Jiao Tong University Library	Research Progress of Mobile Vision Search Technology and its Application Practice in Digital Humanities
	Xu Zhiwei, 2018	Tianjin University Of Technology	Content Analysis of the International Cooperation Practice Project "Excavating Data Challenge"
	Zhao Hongya, 2018	National Library of China	Research on Digital Humanities Project "Leipzig Open Fragment Text Series"
	Yang Helin, Li Bin, Zhu Qiandong	University of Jinan Library	Research on space Construction of the University of Arizona Library
	Fan Huili, Shao Bo, 2017	Nanjing University Library	The Practice Mode and Enlightenment of American University Service Data Lab
	Cao Jinjun, 2018	Tianjin Normal University Library	Digital Humanities concept, project construction, technology use, and evolution process.
	Shi Zhisong, 2018	Shenzhen University Library	Research on the Cooperation Mode of Digital Humanities Development in Universities and Libraries in the Netherlands
	Xu Zhiwei, 2018	Tianjin University of Technology Library	The National Humanities Foundation supports the practice and enlightenment of digital humanities--taking the American Digital Humanities Progress Award as an example
	An Jie, 2018	Fuzhou University Library	Research on Digital Humanities Practice at Columbia University Library
Jin Lingjuan, Han Xi, 2018	Zhejiang University of Water Resources and Electric Power Library	Investigation and Research on the Digital Academic Center of American University Libraries	

	Chen Fangrui, 2017	Fujian Chuanzheng Communications College Library	Research and Enlightenment of Digital Humanities Project Evaluation in American University Libraries
	E Lijun, 2018	Yan Shan University Library	Investigation and Analysis of the Digital Academic Center established by the Research Library Association
Foreign Digital Humanities Education Research	E Lijun, Shan Wei, Chen Shuping, 2018	Yan Shan University Library	Digital Academic Education of North American University Libraries
	Wu Jiaqi, Dong Meixiang, Zhao Zifei, 2018	Nanjing University Of Information Science & Technology Library	Foreign Digital Humanities Graduate Education Survey
	Yang Xiaowei, 2018	Nanjing Medical University Library	Research on Digital Humanities Education in European and American Universities *——Taking the Digital Humanities Department of King's College London as an Example
	Wei Qinghua, 2018	Lanzhou University Library	The Status Quo of European Digital Humanities Education and Its Enlightenment
Foreign Library Participates in Digital Humanities Construction Research	Feng Qing, Chen Huilan, 2016	Donghua University Library	A Review of Foreign Libraries Participating in Digital Humanities Research
	Jin Lingjuan, 2018	Zhejiang University of Water Resources and Electric Power Library	Digital Humanities Librarians' Position Setting in American University Libraries
A Summary of Foreign Digital Humanities Research	Zheng Rui, 2018	Minzu University Of China Library	Analysis of the Status Quo of Global Digital Humanities Development Based on Bibliometrics
	Guo Jing, Wang Xiaoyang, 2018	Shanghai Jiao Tong Jiao Tong University Library Zhejiang University Library	The Evolution and Development Trend of Foreign Digital Humanities Research*——Based on the Harvard University Library Collection Related Monographs
	Li Yu, Liu Hong, Sun Jianjun, 2019	Northwest University Library	Comparative Analysis of Digital Humanities Research at Home and Abroad from the Perspective of Life Cycle

Table 2. Domestic Digital Humanities Construction Research

Author	Library	Main research content
Dong Zheng, Chen Huilan, Zhan Sijia, 2015	Donghua University Library	Investigation and Research on the Status Quo of Textile History Literature Resources under the Background of Digital Humanities
Li Yu, Liu Hong, Sun Jianjun, 2019	Northwest University Library	Comparative Analysis of Digital Humanities Research at Home and Abroad from the Perspective of Life Cycle

Wu Congcong, 2018	Wenzhou Medical University Library	Status Quo of Digital Humanities Research in China Based on CSSCI Core Journals
Huang Gang, 2017	Guangxi University Of Chinese Medicine Library	Analysis of the Status Quo of Subject Service and Digital Humanities Construction in Guangxi University Libraries
Liu Qiong, Lu Zhangping, Li Yonghui, Su Wencheng, 2018	Jiangsu University Library	Frontier and Exploration of Humanities Research in the Age of Big Data——A Summary of the Symposium on "Digital Humanities" of Nanjing University
Zhang Shiyang, 2018	Guangzhou Digital Library	From Recorder to the World Wide Web: The Change of Oral History Technology Carrier and Its Influence
Jin Lingjuan, 2018	Zhejiang University of Water Resources and Electric Power Library	Research on the Status Quo, Barriers, and Countermeasures of Digital Humanities Service in Chinese Libraries
Dong Zhengge, Chen Huilan, 2016	Donghua University Library	Discussion on the Investigation and Development Countermeasures of Digital Humanities Resources

Table 3. Digital Humanities Theory and Methodology

Research Topics	Author	Library	Main research content
Research on Resource Organization and Construction Method Based on Digital Humanities	Lu Shuo, Xie Zhen, 2018	Xi'an Fanyi University Library	Research on the Integration of Information Resources of University Libraries Based on Digital Humanities Service
	Yu Fei, 2018	Nanjing Library	Research on Digital Resource Organization Based on Smart Library——Taking Nanjing Library's Locally developed Resource Library as an Example
	Wang Lei, 2016	Sun Yat-Sen University Library	Huizhou Documents, Hui Studies, and Digital Humanities
	Yang Shanshan, Qin Xiaozhu, Zhang Xingwang, 2017	Guilin University Of Technology Library	The Difficulties and Countermeasures of Digital Construction of Han Buddhism Cultural Heritage
	Fan Jia, 2013	Xihua University Library	The Connotation of "Digital Humanities" and the Deep Development of Digitalization of Ancient Books
	Wu Lihua, Yan Haibin, Fan Yiwen, 2018	Suzhou University of Science and Technology Library	Literature Research of the Republic of China in the Digital Humanities Background
	Liu Wei, Xie Rong, Zhang Lei,	Shanghai Library	National Data Infrastructure for Humanities Research

	Zhang Yongjuan, 2016		
	Wei Xiaoping, 2018	Shanghai University Library	Deep development and utilization of digital ancient books in the digital humanities background
	Wu Fangzhi, 2017	Zhejiang University Library	Digital Research on the Literature of the Republic of China in the Digital Humanities Background
	Yang Guang, 2015	Bayuquan Library	Research on Library Resource Integration Strategy and Application under the Background of Digital Humanities
	Gao Jianhui, 2019	Chuxiong Normal University Library	Research on the Protection of Oral History Data of Minority Nationalities from the Perspective of Digital Humanities
	Xue Huanxue, 2019	Jilin University Library	Development and Construction of Mobile Cultural Relics Database in Library Digital Humanities Project
	Hu Yitao, Hui Fuping, 2019	Nanjing Agricultural University Library	Application of Metadata Method in Digital Humanities Vision*——Taking Agricultural Cultural Heritage as an Example
	Lu Kang, 2018	Nanjing Xiaozhuang University Library	The Practice of Statistical Analysis of Library Readers' Demand and Behavior in Digital Human Environment
	Xia Cuijuan, Bao Bide, 2018	Shanghai Library	Digital Humanities and Network Infrastructure Construction in China Research
Library Digital Humanities Service Research	Wang Dongsheng, Wang Yingfan, 2016	China Foreign Affairs University Library	Research on Digital Humanities Service Strategy of University Library
	Yu Wenwen, 2017	Beijing Sport University Library	Research on Digital Humanities Service of University Libraries Driven by Data
	Huang Yuxin, Wang Yuanzhi, 2017	Hainan Normal University Library, Chongqing Medical and Pharmaceutical College Library	Research on Library Scientific Research Data Service Embedded in Digital Humanities Process
	Hu Aimin, 2018	Hainan Tropical Ocean University Library	Research on the Transformation and Realization Path of Library Classic Reading Promotion Service under the Background of Digital Humanities
	Lai Yongzhong, 2016	The Guizhou University Of Finance and Economics Library	Research on Library Scientific Research Support Service for Digital Humanities
	Zhou Qian, 2015	Luohu Vocational Technology College Library	University Library Service Innovation for Digital Humanities
Research on Digital Humanities Construction in Library	Zeng Xiaoying, 2014	Guangzhou Health Science College Library	Library in the Digital Humanities Background: Role and Service
	Chen Dongyang, 2018	South China Normal University Library	Analysis of Library Space Reengineering Based on Digital Humanities
	Zhu Benjun, Nie Hua, 2017	Beijing University Library	Digital Humanities: A New Direction in Library Practice
	Huang Gang, 2017	Guangxi University Of Chinese Medicine Library	Countermeasure Analysis of Accelerating the Promotion of Subject Service and Digital Humanities Construction in Guangxi University Libraries
	Jiang Meng, 2017	Changzhou College Of Information	Library Digital Humanities Architecture and Strategy Research

		Technology Library	
	Yang Xiaowen, Li Aiguo, 2018	Nanjing Medical University Library, Southeast University Library	Research on the Countermeasure of Digital Humanities Activities in Professional University Libraries——Taking the Library of Nanjing Medical University as an Example
	Li Jie, 2017	Zhejiang University Library	Librarian Role Conversion in the Digital Humanities Background
	Wang Erzhen, 2016	Huanghuai University Library	Digital Humanities and Library Research
	Du Zongming, 2017	Xuzhou Medical University	Library Role Positioning and Practice Path in Digital Humanistic Environment
	Wang Li, 2018	Nanjing Normal University Library	Digital Humanities in University Libraries: A Study of the Difficulties and Countermeasures of Interdisciplinary Cooperation
	Qiao Shanshan, Hu Shengnan, 2018	National University Of Defense Technology Library	Research on Library Development Strategy under the Background of Digital Humanities
Research on Digital Humanities Education in Libraries	Hu Shaojun, 2019	Northeast Petroleum University Library	The Composition of Professional Ability of Digital Humanities Librarians and Training Strategies
	Gui Luomin, Jie Feng, 2018	Shanghai University Library	Research on Digital Humanities Education Demand and Library Participation Model
Digital Human Theory Research	Ou Yangjian, 2018	GuangXi University for Nationalities Library	Digital Humanities Research in Humanities under the Perspective of Big Data
	Peng Donglian, 2006	Central South University Library	On Digital Technology and Humanistic Spirit
	Liu Wei, Ye Ying, 2017	Shanghai Library	Discussion on the Technical System and Theoretical Structure of Digital Humanities
	Rao Junli, 2017	Xi'an University Of Science and Technology Library	The Development of Digital Humanities: From Digital Symbols to Humanities
	Xia Cuijuan, 2019	Shanghai Library	The Wave of Digital Humanities and Cold Thinking
	Xiang Yang, 2016	Shaoyang University Library	Digital Humanities Analysis under the Virtual Community Dimension

Table 4. Digital Humanities Project Practice

Library	Author	Research Content	Digital Humanities Project	Project Description	Project Construction Status
Guangxi University for	Ou Yangjian, 2015	Visual Analysis and Mining of Large-scale Ancient Books Text for Digital Humanities Research	Ancient Digital Humanities Project	The digital humanities platform of ancient books takes the deep development and utilization of ancient books as the starting point,	Under construction (The server is
	Ou Yangjian, 2015	Application of Large-scale Ancient Books Text in			

Nationalities Library		Quantitative Research of Chinese History		exploring new modes of development and application of ancient books, introduces large-scale quantitative calculation and analysis methods, and explores new research paradigms and methods for the application of ancient books in the study of humanities such as linguistics, historical philology, and historical geography. The platform can be used for quantitative analysis and regular discovery in a variety of humanities research fields.	deployed at the E-Institute of comparative linguistics in Shanghai University)
East China Normal University Library	Lu Dan, Li Xin, 2019	Heterogeneous Chronicle Metadata Integration Strategy in Digital Humanities Environment	Heterogeneous Fangzhi Integration Platform(HFIP) project	The Digital Localization Integration Platform is based on the collection of local library resources of the “National Consortium of Normal University Library in China”. The integration includes paper, electronic and digital materials. The contents of the local chronicles include Chinese records, local chronicles, and so on. Create a unified local resources discovery, resource data, digital humanities research literacy teaching and scholar research platform to provide users with platform-based learning, research, communication, and teaching environment.	Phase I Construction Completed
	LuDan, LiXin, 2019	Integrating Heterogeneous Special Resources to Build a Digital Humanities System			
	Li Xin, Zhang Yi, Wang Zhi, 2017	Digital Humanities Research Needs for the Integration of Heterogeneous Special Resources in Libraries			
	Yu Yaxiu, Li Xin, Lu Dan, Cheng Jing, 2017	Innovative Decision Support Service Based on Multi-source Heterogeneous Database Fusion——Taking the Discipline Evaluation System of East China Normal University as an Example			
	Liu Dan, 2017	Design and Implementation of Discovery Platform for Local Chronicles			
	Li Xin, Lu Dan, Cheng Jing, 2018	Data Optimization Based on Crowdsourcing——Taking the Construction of Digital Chance Special Resources as an Example			
	SunYi, Hu Ai, 2018	Construction and Analysis of Institutional Knowledge Base Data Model Based on Multi-Dimensional Association			
Shanghai Jiao Tong University Library	Zhao Siyuan, Tang Meng, 2014	The Classification Method and Basis of the New Tibetan Local Historical Documents of Shanghai Jiao Tong University	China Local History Document Database(CLHDD) project	The inclusion of local literature includes the following 13 categories: contracts, books, servitude, administration, litigation, letters, daily books, and reference books, family gifts, religion, genealogy, drama, educational examinations, and medicine. The total amount will be 350,000 and 1.5 million pages. Establish a specific metadata structure, provide cross navigation, data statistics, and other functions, these features not only help researchers find their own literature, but they are also more	Complete
	Wang Xin, ZhangJie, TangMeng, 2018	A Probe into the Path of Organization and Revelation of Regional Information in Huizhou Contract Documents			
	Li Fang, Chen Jin, Wang Xin, 2014	Digital Construction Planning and Practice of the New Tibetan Local Historical Documents of Shanghai Jiao Tong University			
	Zhang Jie, Li Fang, Tang Meng, 2017	Contract Document Description Metadata Specification Design and Application			
	Li Fang, Tang Meng,	Acquisition and Standardization of Historical			

	Wang Xin, 2018	Geographic Information—Taking the Local Historical Documents of Shanghai Jiao Tong University as an Example		likely to help researchers discover new research topics.	
	Tang Meng, Zhang Jie, 2016	Research on the Process of Local History Document Sorting from the Perspective of Source—Taking the Library of Shanghai Jiao Tong University as an Example			
Shanghai Normal University Library	Cai Yingchun, 2019	Construction and Practice of Bibliographic Data Platform in the Republic of China	Republic of China Bibliographic Data Platform	The main purpose of the "data platform" is to fully reveal all the sub-items of the "original Republic of China literature" and "a new edition of the Republic of China literature". Nearly 1,000 kinds of data have been collected in the "New Edition of the Republic of China Literature". The data cover the joint catalogs of major public libraries and university libraries.	Under construction
	Cai Yingchun, 2019	Digital Construction of Library Special Resources in the Perspective of Digital Humanities—Taking the Literature Catalog Data Platform of the Republic of China as an Example			
	Cai Yingchun, 2019	The Digital Humanistic Realization Path in the Construction of Characteristic Resources—Taking the New Edition of the Bibliographic Digital Platform of the Republic of China as an Example			
Shanghai Library	Xia Cuijuan, Zhang Lei, He Chenzhi, 2017	Library Digital Humanities Project Construction for Knowledge Services: Methods, Processes, and Technologies	Celebrity manuscript archive	It contains more than 240,000 manuscripts and archives of metadata, including more than 120,000 private telegrams, more than 17,000 precious manuscripts, more than 14,000 kinds of treaties, and more than 4,000 contract articles. It also included more than 18,000 kinds of photos and audiovisual materials.	Under construction
	Xia Cuijuan, Lin Haiqing, Liu Wei, 2017	Research and Design of Chinese Ancient Books Data Model for Evidence-Based Practice	Chinese ancient books joint directory and inquiry platform	The platform currently contains catalogs of ancient books in more than 1,400 institutions, and also incorporates official catalogs, historical catalogs, library catalogs, private catalogs, and catalogs. It will combine the analysis of statistics, time and space and social relationship analysis and visualization tools that will be developed soon. The project aims to realize the joint inquiry and standard control of the existing collections of ancient books in each museum, and to provide the evidence-based version of the scholars and the function of the examination mirror.	Complete
	Liu Wei, Lin Haiqing, Xia Cuijuan, 2018	Library Science Method of Digital Humanities Research: Bibliographic Control and Document Evidence			
	Zhang Lei, Xia Cuijuan, 2018	Research on Open Data Service of Library for Digital Humanities—Taking Shanghai Library Open Data	China Genealogy knowledge service	The platform utilizes existing genealogical collection resources and research results to	Complete

		Application Development Competition as an Example	platform(CGKSP) Project	achieve common sense and wisdom's root-seeking services for the general public, knowledge discovery and knowledge mining services for humanities research scholars, as well as bibliographic control and knowledge appreciation for libraries. Resources include more than 54,000 genealogy catalogs included in the China National Genealogy Headquarters.	
	Xia Cuijuan, Zhang Lei, 2016	Application of Linked Data in Family Figures Digital Humanities Service			
	Xia Cuijuan, 2018	The Control of Names in Digital Humanities - Research and Practice			
	Xia Cuijuan, Zhang Lei, 2016	Application of Linked Data in Family Figures Digital Humanities Service			
	Xia Cuijuan, Liu Wei, Chen Tao, Zhang Lei, 2016	Development practice of genealogy associated data service platform			
	Xia Cuijuan, 2017	Research on the Open Application of Chinese Historical Geographic Data in Library Digital Humanities Project			
Sun Yat-Sen University Library	Wang Lei, Xue Yu, Xiao Peng, Shen Bin, 2018	The Construction of Digital Humanities Library in Folk History Documents—Taking the Reflection of Practice in Digital Humanities Library of Huizhou Documents as an Example	Huizhou Document Digital Humanities Project	Provides search portals including property registration number, responsible person, title, abstract, location, time, associated tasks and groups, and types of documents. Analyze search results clustered by means of the document type, time, location, associated characters and groups, and functions such as statistical analysis of related person names and place names involved in the search results.	Under construction

Table 5. Data collection for the three projects of digital humanities

NO.	Library Name	Database Name	Description	Type of Data	classification	Amount	Research Tools	Digital Humanities Training, etc.
1	Shanghai Library	Chinese Genealogy Knowledge Service Platform(CGKSP)	More than 54, 000 kinds of genealogy are included in the Chinese genealogy	Full-Text, Image	chorography	About 54000 records	Time and space distribution tools	have
2	East China Normal University Library	Heterogeneous Fangzhi Integration Platform(HFIP)	Local Records	Full-Text, Full-Text Image	History, Human Geography	67753	Annotation Training/Visualization Tool	have
3	Shanghai Jiao Tong University	Chinese Local Historical Documents Database(CLHDD)	Local Historical Documents of 13 Categories: Contracts, Accounts, and Taxes	Full-Text, Full-Text Image	History, Human Geography	About 35000	Data statistics	have

Table 6. Data collection visits, interviews, and reports

Library name	Time	Place	Research methods	The research subject	Duration
Shanghai Library	2018.12	Shanghai	Interview project leader	Digital humanities project leader (Cuijuan Xia)	About 2 hours
			Visit the work of the project team and ask questions about existing problems	Members of the project team (about 6 people)	About 1 hour
			Listen to the report of the Digital Humanities Project of the Shanghai Library	Shanghai Library Director, Project Leader, Project Technology Leader (about 4 people)	About 4 hours
East China Normal University Library	2018.12	Shanghai	Interview project leader	Digital humanities project leader (Xin Li)	About 2 hours
			Listen to the project leader's digital humanities construction report	Digital humanities project leader (1 person)	About 20 minutes
Shanghai Jiao Tong	2019.03	Shanghai	Interview key participants of the	Major participant of digital humanities	About 1 hour

University	project	project (Jie Zhang)
Library	Listen to the digital humanities construction report of the main participants of the project	Major participant of digital humanities project (1 person) About 20 minutes

Table 7. Survey Results of Locally developed Human Resources Database of 52 Public Libraries

NO.	Library Name	Grade	Name Database	Description	Type of Data	classification	amount	Research tools	Digital Humanities Training, etc.
1	China National Library	National level	Chinese Ancient Books Resource Library	National Library, National Library of France, Tianjin Library Collection of Ancient Books	Full-text Image	History, literature	32277	None	None
			Digital chronicles	Local Records Resources before Qing Dynasty (including Qing Dynasty)	Full-text Image	History, human geography	6529	None	None
			Republic of China Journal	Republic of Chinese Journal	Full-text Image	History, literature	4351	None	None
			Republic of China Books	Book works during the Republic of China	Full-text Image	History, literature	84114	None	None
			Republic of China law	Laws issued during the Republic of China	Full-text Image	History, law	8114	None	None
			Republic of China literature	Books, periodicals, and newspapers during the Republic of China.	Full-text Image	History, literature	About 3520000	None	None
			Inscription	National map inscription resources	Image	History, Art Studies	23639	None	None
			Oracle bone	Oracle bone	Image	History, Linguistics	3764	None	None
			Oracle bone library	Rubble of the oracle bone	Image	History, Linguistics	9277	None	None
			Xixia treatise	Xixia related literature	Abstract Index	History	1202	None	None
			Front shadow	Old Photograph	Image	History	3074	None	None
Collection audio and video library	Domestic and foreign film and television materials, music materials	Audio	Art Studies	11349	None	None			

			and other materials						
			Chinese ancient books Rare Book International Joint Bibliographic System	International Chinese Ancient Books Collection	Catalogue Index	History, Literature	3481	None	None
			East Wenyan Chinese Image Library	More than 4,000 Chinese ancient books collected by the Toyo Culture Research Institute	Full-Text Image	History, Literature	3730	None	None
			Harvard University Shanben special possession	Harvard University Harvard Yenching Library Collection of Chinese Rare Books Ancient Books	Full-Text Image	History	1139	None	None
			Minority resource pool	Includes special resources of the Qinghai Provincial Library	Image, Video	History, Human geography, Ethnology	1199	None	None
			ancient books and records	ancient books and records collection	Full-Text Image	History, Literature	1084	None	None
			Republic of China newspaper	North China Daily / Dagang Daily / Xinhua Daily / Yi Shi Bao	Full-Text Image	History, Literature	9433	None	None
			Local video resource database	Thematic videos from 19 local libraries	Video	Human geography	5487	None	None
			Old Photographs	A collection of Old Photographs	Image	History	81687	None	None
			Pedigree	Hubei Library, Liaoning Provincial Library, Qinghai Library Collection full-text Database	Full-Text Image	Genealogy	2267	None	None
			Local Republic of China literature	Documents of the Republic of China including eight libraries	Full-Text Image	History, Literature, Human geography	63267	None	None
			Local Chronicles	Including the local chronicles of Shaanxi, Shandong, Hubei and other places,	Full-Text Image	History, Human geography	2398	None	None
			Local collection characteristic resources	Shandong, Heilongjiang, Jilin and other provincial pavilions have unique resources	Image, Video	History, Human geography	21081	None	None
2	Liaoning Provincial Library	Provincial	Guandong celebrity database	Introduction to Guandong undefined celebrity.	Text	History	12755	None	None
			September 18th Incident Data Index Library	September 18th Incident Data Index	Reference Index	History	8498	None	None
			Qing History Picture Database	Qing History Picture	Image	History	4949	None	None

			The people's Daily of the three provinces in Northeast China	The people's Daily of the three provinces in Northeast China	Full-Text Image	History, Literature	203861	None	None
			Taidong Daily	Taidong Daily	Full-Text Image	History, Literature	10342	None	None
			Northeast daily database	Northeast daily	Full-Text Image	History, Literature	137561	None	None
			Northeast Local Records Biographical Data of the Figures	Northeast Local Records Biographical Data of the Figures	Full-Text Image	History, Human geography	39304	None	None
			Northeast Pictorial Database	Northeast Pictorial	Full-Text Image	History, Literature	9205	None	None
			Northeast Anti-Japanese War Photo Gallery	Northeast Anti-Japanese War Pictures	Image	History	1711	None	None
			Liaoning Writers' Works Library in the 1930s	Liaoning writers' library of works for 30 years	Full-Text Image	Literature	3058	None	None
			Mantie Railway Company data bibliography database	Mantie Railway Company Bibliography	Bibliographical List	History	25701	None	None
			Peace daily	Peace daily	Full-Text Image	History, Literature	56941	None	None
			Wake up the Times	Wake up the Times	Full-Text Image	History, Literature	14289	None	None
			Northeast War of Resistance against Japan Book Index Library	Book catalog of Northeast War of Resistance against Japan	Catalogue Index	History, Human geography	1867	None	None
			Japanese Book of the Republic of China	Japanese books and materials in the Republic of China	Full-Text Image	History, Linguistics	2369	None	None
			Pictures of the Party History of the Communist Party of China	Pictures of the Party History of the Communist Party of China	Image	History	1274	None	None

			Central Daily News	Central Daily News	Full-Text Image	History, Literature	18746	None	None
			Shengjing Times	Shengjing Times	Full-Text Image	History, Literature	1498467	None	None
			Nanjing Library Collection Rarely Local Records Full-text Image Database	Local Records	Full-Text Image	History, Literature, Human geography	20	None	None
			National Day of the Killing of the Nanjing Massacre	Nanjing Massacre Information	Text, Image	History	About 20000	None	None
			? Jiangsu Writersundefined works Database	Jiangsu writer information	Text, Image	History, Human geography	17453	None	None
			Jiangsu old newspapers database	Old newspapers in Jiangsu	Full-Text Image	History, Literature, Human geography	About 3000	None	None
			Jiangsu Province Unmovable Cultural Relics Database	Immovable cultural relics data	Text,Image,Video	History, Human geography	15128	None	None
			Revolutionary Memories	Red Revolution related materials	Text, Image	History	2280	None	None
			Jiangsu Culture Database	Jiangsu history, culture, folk customs, and other information	Text, Image	History, Human geography	40882	None	None
			Chinese Modern Document Image Database	Images in modern literature	Text, Image	History	About 10000	None	None
			Chinese Nationality Database	National costumes, scenery architecture, etc.	Text, Image	History, Human geography	2118	None	None
			Ancient Chinese Sports Picture Library	Ancient Chinese sports pictures	Text, Image	History, Sports Science	1477	None	None
			Centennial Arts Garden	Chinese painting, comics, western painting, sculpture, calligraphy, etc.	Text, Image	Art Studies	28155	None	None
			Centennial character	Nearly a hundred years of people pictures and introductions	Text, Image	History	3046	None	None
3	Nanjing Library	Provincial							
4	Capital Library	Provincial	Ancient book illustration library	ancient book illustration	Image	History	About 10000	None	None
			Image Database of rare and good	Ancient books	Full-Text Image	History, Literature	500000	None	None

			Books in Ancient Books						
5	Tianjin Library	Provincial	Historical literature digital resources	Ancient Book Resources	Full-Text Image	History, Literature	About 1500	None	None
6	Shanghai Library	Provincial	Catalog of genealogy collected in Shanghai Library	Chinese genealogy catalog	Catalogue Index	chorography	About 110000	None	None
			Shanghai Years	Materials on the changes of style and Culture in Shanghai	Text, Image, Video, Audio	History, Human geography	About 10000	None	None
			Shanghai Library Open data platform	The Open Data Platform of the Digital Humane Project of the Shanghai Library	Video, Image, Text, Audio, Catalogue Index	Integrated Platform	Integrated Platform	Data conversion tool / basic knowledge base, etc.	have
			Chinese Genealogy Knowledge Service Platform (CGKSP)	More than 54,000 kinds of genealogy are included in the Chinese genealogy	Full-Text, Image	chorography	About 54000	Time and space distribution tools	have
			Sheng Xuanhuai Archives knowledge Base	Sheng Xuanhuai family diary, manuscript, letter, etc.	Full-Text Image	History, Literature	About 157000	None	None
			Chinese ancient books joint directory and inquiry platform	Catalog of ancient books in more than 1,400 institutions	Catalogue Index	History, Literature	More than 1,400 institutions	None	None
			Celebrity Manuscript Archives	manuscripts, archives, etc.	Full-Text	History, Literature	About 240000	None	None
			Chinese old film knowledge base	The work of old Chinese films	Text, Image, Video	History, Art Studies	About 13000	None	None
			Red documentary library	Red historical literature	Text, Catalogue Index	History	31485	None	None
7	Chongqing Library	Provincial	Bayu celebrity	Materials of local celebrities in Chongqing	Text, Image	History	20	None	None
8	Hebei Library	Provincial	None						
9	Shanxi Library	Provincial	Dazhai literature titles	Dazhai-related literature titles	Thematic Index	Human geography	2572	None	None
			Collection of	Shanxi historical resources	Thematic Index	History, Human	2800	None	None

			Shanxi literature and history materials			geography			
			Shanxi Province Local Chronicles Abstract	Local Chronicles	Catalogue Index	History, Human geography	1024	None	None
10	Jilin Provincial Library	Provincial	Jilin Province local characteristic resource video library.	Video of Local characteristic Resources in Jilin Province	Text, Video, Audio	History, Human geography, Art Studies	2327	None	None
			Jilin drama culture multimedia resource library	Jilin drama culture multimedia resource library	Text, Video, Audio	Art Studies	1115	None	None
			Jilin two people transfer database	Two-person transfer related information	Text, Video, Audio	Art Studies	2694	None	None
11	Heilongjiang Provincial Library	Provincial	Heilongjiang drama multimedia resource library	Heilongjiang drama related information	Text, Image, Video	Art Studies	About 1000	None	None
			Helen paper cutting	Paper-cut folk culture art	Text, Image, Video	Art Studies	About 1000	None	None
			Wangkui shadow play	Shadow play art resources	Text, Image, Video	Art Studies	About 1000	None	None
12	Zhejiang Library	Provincial	Jiayetang engraving database	Engraving photo gallery	Image	History, Art Studies	About 10000	None	None
			Guohou City and County Newspapers (1949-1972)	The full-text version of the county newspaper after the founding of the Zhejiang Library	Full-Text Image	History, Literature	About 80000	None	None
			Rubbing database	Digitization of collection and expanding film.	Text, Image	History, Literature	About 2006	None	None
			Precious ancient books database	Precious ancient books	Text, Image	History, Literature	About 137635	None	None
			Zhejiang Water Application text-Multimedia Resource Database of Zhejiang Academy of Sciences	Zhejiang Academy School and other related media databases	Text, Image, Video	History, Human geography	About 1000	None	None
			Chinese historical image database	Contains images of Chinese historical figures	Image	History	5928	None	None

			Zhejiang Library Genealogy Database	Zhejiang genealogy	Catalogue Index, Image	Genealogy	26574	None	None
			Chinese character Seal Database of the past dynasties	Seal of the characters of the past dynasties in China	Text, Image	History	About 30000	None	None
			Database of statues of Chinese temples and ancestral views	Statues of temples and shrines in various parts of China	Text, Image	science of religion	About 14000	None	None
			Chinese Opera facial Image Database	The colorful ancient costumes and operas of the past dynasties in China are dressed as well as faces	Text, Image	Art Studies	About 20000	None	None
13	Anhui Provincial Library	Provincial	Anhui fine arts	Calligraphy, Chinese painting, seal cutting, etc.	Text,Image	Art Studies	3994	None	None
			Bonfire Jianghuai	Anhui red classic old photos	Text, Image	History	1346	None	None
14	Fujian Provincial Library	Provincial	Fujian Yanhuang vertical and horizontal	Fujian Yanhuang vertical and horizontal journal	Full-Text Image	Human geography, Ethnology	1500	None	None
15	Jiangxi Provincial Library	Provincial	Jiangxi Historical and Cultural Celebrity Resource Library	Jiangxi historical and cultural celebrity information	Text,Image,Video,	History	2462	None	None
			Collection of Chinese Journals before the founding of the People's Republic of China	Pre-Foundation Chinese Journal	Catalogue Index	History	2370	None	None
			Republic of China literature	Republic of China Literature Resources	Catalogue Index	History, Literature	28480	None	None
			local chronicle	local chronicle Query	Catalogue Index	History, Human geography	1230	None	None
			Local characteristic literature	Local characteristic literature inquiry	thematic Index	History, Human geography	1866	None	None
16	Shandong Provincial Library	Provincial	Shandong Historical Characters Resource Library	Shandong historical figures	Text, Image	History, Human geography	23236	None	None
17	Henan Provincial Library	Provincial	Local literature library	Henan local literature resources	Full-Text Image	History, Literature, Human geography	About 30000	None	None
			Henan Quyi Multimedia	Quyi resources	Video,Text,Image	Art Studies	About 1000	None	None

			Resource Library						
18	Hubei Provincial Library	Provincial	Taoism and Wudang Mountains	Wudang Relevant Information	Text,Image,Video	science of religion	1567	None	None
			Red history and culture	Red history and culture related materials, related videos	Text,Image,Video	History	1244	None	None
			Hubei Opera Multimedia Resource Library	Han drama, Chu opera, Huagu opera, and another repertoire	Text,Image,Video, Audio	Art Studies	5952	None	None
19	Hunan Library	Provincial	Ancient Residences in Ancient Villages and Towns of Hunan Province	Ancient Residence Data of Ancient Villages and Towns in Hunan Province	Text,Image,Video, Audio	History, Human geography	8648	None	None
			Video of Xiangtu	Xiangtu drama and other videos	Video	Art Studies	About 2000	None	None
20	Zhongshan Library of Guangzhou Province	Provincial	Local Literature Picture Database	Guangzhou History Pictures, Revolution Pictures of 1911, Scholars' Charm, etc.	Image	History, Human geography	5586	None	None
			Miniature Document Full Text Database	Collection of miniature ancient books, periodicals, newspapers, and documents	Full-Text Image	History, Literature	About 1000000	None	None
			Multimedia Database of "Newspaper, Map, and View of Guangdong"	The News Pictures of Guangdong in the Lithographic Newspapers of the Late Qing Dynasty and the Early Republic of China	Full-Text Image	History, Literature, Human geography	About 2300	None	None
			Guangzhou Grand Ceremony	Classics, History, Subjects, Collections, and Clusters	Full-Text, Full-Text Image	History, Literature	4064	None	None
21	Hainan Provincial Library	Provincial	None						
22	Sichuan Provincial Library	Provincial	None						
23	Guizhou Provincial Library	Provincial	Bibliographic Library of Books in the Republic of China	Bibliography of Books in the Republic of China	Image	History	About 5000	None	None
24	Yunnan Provincial Library	Provincial	None						

25	Shaanxi Provincial Library	Provincial	Red Memory Event Library in Shaanxi-Gansu-Ningxia Border Region	Shaanxi, Gansu and Ningxia Border Area events, conferences, battles, battles, etc.	Text,Video, Audio,Image	History,Human geography	2819	None	None
			Red Memory Yanan Spirit Library in Shaanxi-Gansu-Ningxia Border Region	Yan'an Spirit Library	Text,Image,Video, Audio	History	2652	None	None
			Shaanxi-Gansu-Ningxia Border Region Red Memory Reserch Literature Library	The literature on Red Memory Research in Shaanxi-Gansu-Ningxia Border Region	Text,Image,Video, Audio	History	2102	None	None
			Silk Road Multimedia Resource Library	Silk Road-related information	Text, Video, Audio, Image	History, Human geography	About 10000	None	None
			Talking about Shaanxi Business Database	Shaanxi Business Information	Text,Image,Video	History, Human geography	3668	None	None
			Shaanxi Buddhist Cultural Resources Treasury	Introduction to Shaanxi Buddhist Culture	Text, Image	science of religion	10744	None	None
			Xi'an Incident	Xi'an Incident Related Information	Text,Image	History	6240	None	None
			Shaanxi Imperial Mausoleum Database	The material of Shaanxi Imperial Mausoleum	Text, Image	History, Human geography	3503	None	None
			Qin Cavity Qin Yun Database.	Qin Cavity Qin Yun Relevant Information	Text,Image,Video, Audio	Art Studies	2729	None	None
			Shaanxi Literature and History DataBase	Shaanxi Literature and History Materials	Text, Image	History, Literature, Human geography	3802	None	None
	Provincial Literature Library	Shaanxi Province related materials	Text, Image	History, Human geography	14438	None	None		
26	Gansu Provincial Library	Provincial	Northwest local literature journal library	Bibliographic information of local journals in the northwest of China during the period of the Republic of China	Title Index	History, Human geography	6839	None	None
			Northwest Local Literature	Collection of newspapers and periodicals from 1905 to 1990	Contents Index	History	27499	None	None

			Newspaper Title Index Database						
			Northwest local literature, ancient books, rare books, full-text database	Information on Political Experience, History, and Culture in Shaanxi and Other Five Provinces and Areas	Thematic Index	History, Literature, Human geography	1051	None	None
			Northwest local document image database	Northwest local literature pictures	Text, Image	History, Human geography	4392	None	None
			Northwest local literature and newspaper library	Collection of bibliographic information of local newspapers in Northwest China since the Republic of China	Title Index	History, Human geography	About 5000	None	None
			Imperial Collection of Four Research Resource Database	Imperial Collection of Four Research	Text, Image	History, Literature	6104	None	None
			Local literature joint bibliographic database	Local bibliography of Gansu Province and 14 prefectures and counties	Catalogue Index	History, Human geography	1817	None	None
			Situation of Gansu Province	Relevant Data of Gansu Province	Text	History, Human geography, science of religion	2271	None	None
27	Qinghai Provincial Library	Provincial	Local History	Local History Chronicles of Qinghai Province	Full-text	History, Human geography	About 12181	None	None
28	Inner Mongolia Library	Provincial	Collection of Works of Cultural Celebrities	Calligraphy, Photography, Painting, Sculpture, Seal Carving	Text, Image	Art Studies	1270	None	None
			Characteristic Collection Database	Mongolian and Chinese literature and ancient literature	Text, Image	History, Literature, Human geography, Linguistics	678	None	None
29	Guangxi Zhuang Autonomous Region Library	Provincial	Guangxi Republican characters	Information and photos of the Republic of China anti-Japanese generals and other Republican figures	Text, Image	History	1181	None	None
			Bagui poetry	Historical poems	Video, Text	History, Literature	About 5800	None	None
30	Ningxia Library	Provincial	Ningxia Rock Painting Multimedia Database	Ningxia Rock Painting Literature Information Resources	Text, Image	History, Human geography, Art Studies	About 26000	None	None
			Red memory multimedia resource	Revolutionary deeds and ruins of Ningxia	Image	History	1123	None	None

			library						
31	Xinjiang Autonomous Region Library	Provincial	None						
32	Tibet Autonomous Region Library	Provincial	None						
33	Harbin Library	city level	Middle East Railway	The Middle East Railway Album from the library collection	Image	History	2245	None	None
			Chinese local newspaper index before the founding of the library	《Chinese local newspaper index before the founding of the library》	Catalogue Index	History, Literature	51379	None	None
			Local literature full-text database	58 local documents in the library collection	Full-Text Image	History, Literature, Human geography	58	None	None
			Full-text newspaper database before the founding	The full collection of local newspapers published before 1949 in the library collection	Full-Text Image	History, Literature	68	None	None
34	Changchun Library	city level	Northeast Local Literature Index Database	The literature of the Northeast and Manchuria in the Japanese-Puppet Period of the Library Collection	Catalogue Index	History, Literature, Human geography	About 3000	None	None
35	Shenzhen Library	city level	Shenzhen Photo Gallery	News photos published in the Shenzhen Special Zone Daily before 2002	Image	History, Literature, Human geography	3000	None	None
			Collection of rare books database	Scanned copies of rare ancient books collected in the library	Image	History, Literature	47	None	None
36	Guangzhou Library	city level	Guangzhou Historical Bibliographic Database	Canons History Child, Set, Cluster Department	Text, Image	History, Literature	8250	None	None
37	Nanchang Library	city level	None					None	None
38	Jinan Library	city level	Chinese classics	Classical Chinese sentence	Text, Image	Literature	About 600	None	None
39	Nanning Library	city level	None						
40	Changsha Library	city level	None						
41	Hohhot Library	city level	None						

42	Xining Library	city level	None						
43	Zhengzhou Library	city level	None						
44	Shijiazhuang Library	city level	None						
45	Wuhan Library	city level	None						
46	Lanzhou Library	city level	None						
47	Taiyuan Library	city level	Taiyuan Local Document Characteristic Library	Fu Shan、Jin Memorial Temple etc.	Text, Image	History, Human geography	About 10000	None	None
48	Hefei Library	city level	None					None	None
49	Chengdu Library	city level	Chengdu Digital Museum of Intangible Cultural Heritage	Chengdu Intangible Cultural Heritage Information	Text, Image	History, Human geography	About 1200	None	None
50	Xi'an Library	city level	None					None	None
51	Fuzhou Library	city level	Fuzhou Local Literature Database	Includes major memorabilia and related figures from Fuzhou	Text	History, Human geography	11593	None	None
52	Hangzhou Library	city level	Liangzhu Culture Series Database	Liangzhu Culture related materials	Image	History, Human geography	About 4000	None	None
			Hangzhou local literature	Hangzhou local literature	Image, Text	History, Human geography	About 3000	None	None
			Local literature database	Hangzhou Local Chronicles、Hangzhou Range Rover、Hangzhou in the Republic of China etc.	Image, Text	History, Human geography	About 3000	None	None

Table 8. Survey Results of Locally developed Human Resources Database of 100 University Libraries

NO.	Library Name	Database Name	Description	Type of Data	classification	Amount	Research Tools	Digital Humanities Training
1	Tsinghua University libr	Digital Library Database of Chinese	China's history of science and technology	Full-Text Image,	History,	About	None	None

	ary	History of Science and Technology		Text, Image, Abstract Index	mathematics	64000		
		Characteristic Resources of Digital Center	LB Handbook, Republic of China Journal Financial Library	Full-Text Image	History, literature, Art, Economics	About 60000	None	None
2	Beijing University library	Ancient Literature Resource Bank of Colleges and Universities	Ancient Books and Documents	Book Index	History, literature	About 880000	None	None
		Yan Da's Paper	Bachelor's and Master's Paper of Yanjing University	Image	History	About 2600	None	None
		Old Newspapers and Periodicals of Late Qing and Republic of China	Old Newspapers and Periodicals of Late Qing and Republic of China	Image	History, Literature	554486	None	None
		Historical Geography of Beijing	Historical and Geographical Data of Beijing	Text,Image,Video ,Audio	History, Human geography	2791	None	None
3	Zhejiang University	Ancient Books and Documents	Ancient Books Service、 Ancient Literature Resources Network、 Collection of precious ancient books	Book Index	History, Literature	About 187000	None	None
		Large Document Information Base of Zhejiang University	It involves literature, history, philosophy, language, and many other fields.	Book Index	Comprehensive	56642	None	None
4	Fudan University	Ancient Documents	Collection of Thread-bound Ancient Books	Text, Image	History, Literature	400000	None	None
		Fudan Library	Fudan Scholars, Library Collection, Alumni Style and Library Dynamics	Text, Image	History, Literature, Education	2592	None	None
5	Renmin University of China Libraries	Database of Ancient Books in the Library	Ancient Books	Book Index	History, Literature	24105	None	None
		Press clippings database	Newspapers, periodicals of the whole country, provinces, major cities, etc.	Full-Text Image	History, Literature	1151064	None	None
		Characteristic Music Database of Renmin University of China	Special Music Album	Video	Art	1255	None	None
		Library Resource Bank in the Period of the Republic of China	Books of the Republic of China and Liberated Areas Publications	title Index	History, Literature	48684	None	None
		Periodical Resource Bank in the Period of the Republic of China	Books of the Republic of China and Liberated Areas Publications	title Index	History, Literature	5815	None	None
6	Library of Shanghai Jiao Tong University	China Chamber of Commerce Archives Database	Trade union rosters/payrolls, checkbooks and questionnaires	Full-Text, Full-Text Image	History, Economics	About 50000	None	None
		Chinese Local Historical Documents Database	Local Historical Documents of 13 Categories: Contracts, Accounts, and Taxes	Full-Text, Full-Text Image	History, Human	About 35000	Data statistics	have

					Geography			
		China Judicial Archives Database—Jiangjin Volume	Marriage disputes, tax violations, debt disputes	Full-Text, Full-Text Image	History, Law	About 18000	None	None
		Tokyo Trial Documents Database	Court Records, Court Records, Evidence, Research Materials, Video, and Audio Materials	Text,Video,Image	History	About 12000	None	None
7	Wuhan University Library	Yangtze River resource library	Information Resources in the Yangtze River Basin	Text, Image	History, Human Geography	About 250000	None	None
8	Nanjing University Library	None					None	None
9	Jilin University Library	Full-text Library of Northeast Local Chronicles	Local Chronicles of Northeast China	Full-Text Image	History, Human Geography	2935	None	None
		American Civil Liberties Alliance Archives	American Civil Liberties Alliance Archives	Full-Text Image	History, Human Geography	10954	None	None
		Literature Database of Epigraphy in the Republic of China	Literature of Epigraphy	title Index	History, Archaeology	2990	None	None
		Jilin University Ancient Books Library	Ancient Books and Documents	title Index	History, Literature	33969	None	None
10	Sun Yat-sen University Library	Full-text Database of Periodicals in the Republic of China	Periodicals since the late Qing Dynasty and before 1949	Full-Text Image	History, Literature	About 60000	None	None
		Ancient Books Description System in University Ancient Documents Resource Base	Bibliography of Good Books and Bibliography of Ordinary Ancient Books	Book Index	History, Literature	About 50000	None	None
11	Library of Huazhong University of Science and Technology	None						
12	Sichuan University Library	Ancient Literature Resource Bank of Colleges and Universities	The collection of ancient literature resources in university libraries including Peking University, Beijing Normal University, Nanjing University, and Sichuan University	Full-Text Image	History, Literature	202449	None	None
		New News database	New News from 1930 to 1950	Full-Text Image	History, Literature	About 910000	None	None

		International Cooperation Plan for Digitalization of Chinese and English Books in Colleges and Universities	Ancient Books, Republican Books, Republican Periodicals, Paintings, English Books	Full-Text Image, Directory Index	History, Literature, Art	About 2500000	None	None
13	Tianjin University Library	None					None	None
14	Library of Nankai University	"Corporate Governance" Thematic Research Database	Information on Corporate Governance	Audio,Image,Video	Management	15120	None	None
14	Library of Xi'an Jiao Tong University	None						
16	Library of China University of Science and Technology	None						
17	Central South University Library	None						
18	Library of Harbin University of Technology	None						
19	Beijing Normal University Library	Full Library of Books of the Republic of China	Books of the Republic of China	Full-Text Image	History, Literature	11822	None	None
		Characteristic Library of Beijing Normal University	Beijing Normal School Scholars, Alumni Yinghua, Writing and Ink Authentic Works, Collection of Works, etc.	Video,Text,Image	Literature,Art	5429	None	None
		Collection of Ancient Books Database	Ancient Books	Book Index	History, Literature	42461	None	None
		Poetry Collection Database of Qing Dynasty	Collected Works of Qing Dynasty	title Index	History, Literature	2023	None	None
		Full-text Title Author Index	Text Collection	title Index	History, Literature, linguistics	33728	None	None
		Line-mounted Local Chronicle Database	Local Records	title Index		2898	None	None
		Full-textbook Library of Normal Schools and Primary and Secondary Schools before Liberation	Pre-liberation textbooks	Text, Image	Education	2626	None	None
20	Shandong University Library	Pang Pu's Book Collection	Ancient Books	Book Index	History, Literature	7331	None	None

21	Xiamen University Library	Xiamen University Institutional Repository	Academic works, periodical papers, working manuscripts, etc.	Full-Text Image, Text	Comprehensive	118052	None	None
		Southeast China Sea database	Diaoyu Island Problem	Bibliographic Index,Text,Image, Video,Audio	History, Human Geography	About 500000	None	None
		Xiamen University Library	Xiamen University Library	title Index	Comprehensive	About 4000	None	None
		Legal Academic Database	The latest legal research materials collected by Xiamen University scholars from overseas	Image,Texts	Law	About 300000	None	None
22	Tongji University Library	Digital Collection	Publication of books and Dissertations in 1964	Full-Text Image, Directory Index	History, Literature	About 7000	None	None
		Tongji Library	Relevant Information of Tongji People	Image, catalog Index	History, Literature	About 3000	None	None
23	Library of Beijing Aerospace University	None						
24	Library of Dalian University of Technology	None						
25	Northeast University Library	Zhang Xueliang Literature Database	Zhang Xueliang Literature Database	Photo, Bibliographic Index	History	40000	None	None
26	East China University of Technology Library	None					None	None
27	East China Normal University Library	Library of Local Records of East China Normal University	Ordinary Books, Ancient Books, Lined Books, CD-ROMs, and E-Books	Full-Text Image, Directory Index	History, Human Geography	48913	None	None
		Heterogeneous Fangzhi Integration Platform(HFIP)	Local Records	Full-Text, Full-Text Image	History, Human Geography	67753	Annotation Training /Visualization Tool	have
		Wang Zhiliang Digital Library	Major works, manuscripts, paintings, books, etc.	Text,Image,Video	History,Edu cation	2819	None	None
28	Library of Beijing University of	None						

	Technology							
29	Library of Beijing University of Chemical Technology	None						
30	Library of Beijing Jiao Tong University	Linear Bibliographic Library of Ancient Books	Ancient Works	Book Index	History, Literature	About 2000	None	None
		Journals of the Republic of China Railway	Various journals related to railways are included.	Text	History	33 titles	None	None
		Digital Railway Museum	The Digital Railway Museum mainly contains railway historical stories and so on.	Text, Image	History	About 1000	None	None
31	Library of Beijing University of Science and Technology	None						
32	Library of Beijing Institute of Technology	None						
33	Library of Beijing Forestry University	Beijing Forestry University Staff Library	The school's faculty and staff of various types of academic achievements.	Title Index	Comprehensive	23496	None	None
		Beijing Forestry University Library Collection Photo Gallery	Pictures of architectural design, round neck building, architectural art environment, urban planning, garden planning, etc.	image	Art	About 30000	None	None
34	Beijing Union Medical College Hospital Library	None						
35	Beijing University of Posts and Telecommunications Library	China's modern postal and telecommunications history special resource library	Historical documents related to the history of China's post and telecommunications	Full-Text image	History	32000	None	None
36	University of Electronic Science and Technology Library	Academic library	"Chengdian's Works Collection," "Personal Collection," etc.	Text,Image	Comprehensive	19613	None	None
37	Northeast Normal University Library	Northeast Literature Photo Gallery	Pictures of the northeast	image	History, Archaeology	8960	None	None
38	Donghua University Library	None					None	None
39	Southeast University Library	Guoding Library	The writings donated by Mr. Li Guoding	Title Index	economics	1700	None	None

40	University of International Business and Economics Library	None						
41	Fujian Normal University Library	Collection of 36 New Local Records Biography Catalogues in Fujian Province	Local history biography	Directory Index	History, Literature, Human Geography	2149	None	None
		Chinese and foreign books in the Republic of China	Books of the Republic of China	Full-Text image	History, Literature	104525	None	None
		Library of the Republic of China Chinese literature characteristic database	Chinese characteristic literature	Full-Text image, abstract	History, Literature	178800	None	None
		Hong Kong, Macao, and Taiwan collections library	Collection of books	Bibliographic Index	History, Literature	9300	None	None
42	Fuzhou University Library	Belt and Road Database	Information library, theoretical database, national library, provincial database, special library, index library, history library, expert database	Text, Image	History, Human Geography	23942	None	None
43	Guangxi University Library	None						
44	Harbin Engineering University Library	None						
45	Hangzhou University of Electronic Science and Technology Library	None						
46	Hefei University of Technology Library	None						
47	Hohai University Library	Digital literature on water conservancy ancient books	Ancient books on water conservancy	Full-Text image	History	About 2216	None	None
		None					None	None
48	Hunan University	Financial literature database	Financial literature database	Text	economics	About 400000	None	None
		Li Youzeng Collection Database	Li Youzeng Collection Resources	Text, Image	History, Literature	About 1000	None	None
		College Culture Database	College Cultural Materials	Text, Image	History, Literature	About 7000	None	None
49	Hunan Normal University Library	None						

50	South China University of Technology Library	None						
51	South China Agricultural University Library	South China Agricultural University Expert Library	The library contains published literature published by many experts and scholars from various disciplines in South China Agricultural University.	Full-Text image	Economics, Education, Economics	10106	None	None
		Library of the Republic of China literature full-text database	Collection of agricultural literature during the Republic of China	Full-Text image	History, Literature	14181	None	None
52	South China Normal University Library	None						
53	Huazhong Agricultural University Library	None						
54	Central China Normal University Database	China Rural Research Literature Database	China's rural issues related to literature	Text, Image	Education, Economics	About 3000	None	None
55	Jinan University Library	Overseas Chinese Literature Information Database	Overseas Chinese Research Resources	Directory Index, Image, Abstract, Full-Text	History, Human Geography, Ethnology	About 15000	None	None
		Zhang Taiyan Collection	Mr. Zhang Taiyan's ancient books collected during his lifetime	Summary Index	History, Literature	About 4000	None	None
		Jinan Library	Jinan people's works, non-book materials, collections	Summary Index	History, Literature	About 5572	None	None
56	Jiangnan University Library	Han nationality folk costumes featured database	Clothing pictures, etc.	Text, Image	History, Art	6866	None	None
57	Kunming University of Science and Technology Library	None						
58	Lanzhou University	Dunhuang Digital Library	The suicide notes, murals, colored sculptures, enamel paintings, historical sites, etc. involved in Dunhuang studies	Text, Image, title Index	History, Human Geography, Literature	About 120000	None	None
59	Nanchang University Library	None						
60	Nanjing University of Aeronautics Library	None						
61	Nanjing Agricultural University Library	Nannong Library	Books, books, classes, activities, journals	Text, Image, Audio	Comprehensive	34163	None	None

62	Nanjing Normal University Library	Republic of China Education Journal	Part of the books and periodicals of the former Central University and other institutions	Text, Image	History, Literature, Education	149kinds	None	None
63	Ningbo University Library	None						
64	Shanxi University Library	None						
65	Shanxi Normal University Library	Teacher education book database	Ancient Books of the Republic of China and Hong Kong and Taiwan Education Books	Full-Text image	History, Literature, Education	About 4000	None	None
		Northwest Local History Database	Local History documents	Full-Text image	History, Human Geography	About 2000	None	None
66	Shanghai University of Finance and Economics Library	None						
67	Shanghai University Library	None						
68	Shanghai University of Technology Library	None						
69	Shenzhen University Library	None						
70	Capital Normal University Library	None						
71	Capital Medical University Library	None						
72	Suzhou University Library	Suzhou University Ancient Books Resource Database	Ancient books	Full-Text image	History, Literature	14128	None	None
		Ancient rhyme and current wind multimedia video database	World heritage, opera music, etc.	Video	Art		None	None
		Wu Culture Database	Historical celebrities, Kunqu opera, gardens, etc.	Text,Image	History,Hu man Geography, Art	25435	None	None
		Chinese Celebrity Image Database	Portraits, historical materials, collections, monuments, etc.	Text,Image,Audio	History,Lite rature	6313	None	None
73	Tianjin Normal University Library	None						

74	Wuhan University of Technology Library	None						
75	Xi'an University of Electronic Science and Technology Library	None						
76	Northwestern University Library	None						
77	Northwestern Polytechnical University Library	None						
78	Northwest A&F University Library	Ancient books library	Ancient books, Republic of China, contemporary research literature	Text, Image	History, Literature	About 30000	None	None
79	Southwestern University of Finance and Economics Library	Southwestern University of Finance and Economics	Permanent Exhibition / Special Exhibition	Text,Image,Audio	History, Economics	5146	None	None
80	Southwest University Library	None						
81	Southwest Jiao Tong University Library	None						
82	Yanshan University Library	A special collection of literature resources	A special collection of literature resources	Full-Text image	History, Literature	About 110000	None	None
83	Yangzhou University Library	Yangda Library	Bibliography	Bibliographic Index	Education	3267	None	None
		Yangzhou Culture Database	Academic, religious, literary, artistic, tourism, etc.	Text,Image	History,Literature,Art	12727	None	None
84	Yunnan University Library	Apabi Digital Resource Platform	Republic of China journals, ethnology, journalism, etc.	Text,Image	Comprehensive	82124	None	None
85	Chang'an University Library	None						
86	Zhejiang University of Technology Library	None						
87	Zhejiang Normal University Library	Teacher education characteristic resource database	Teacher education-related resources	Text,Video,Audio	Education	132136	None	None
88	Zhejiang Normal University Library	African research database	African research materials	Text, Image	History, Human Geography	23302	None	None
89	Zhengzhou University Library	None						

90	China University of Geosciences Library	None						
91	Ocean University of China Library	None						
92	China University of Mining and Technology Library	China Coal Mine Literature and History Library	Chinese coal mine literature and history materials	image	History	8785	None	None
93	China Agricultural University Library	Old collection of collections	Ancient books, Republic of China journals, Republic of China books, English books	Full-Text image	History, Literature	About 7000	None	None
94	China University of Petroleum Library	National Petroleum Experts and Scholars Academic Resources Database	Petroleum experts and scholars	Text,Image,Video	Comprehensive	About 221616	None	None
95	China University of Political Science and Law Library	Legal Review Weekly	Collecting the precious materials of the "Legal Review" weekly magazine from 1923 to 1937 before the War of Resistance Against Japanese Aggression	image	History, Law	7555	None	None
96	Zhongnan University of Economics and Law University Library	Chinese re-created rare books	Rare books	Directory Index	History, Literature	About 1000	None	None
		The old paperback catalog of the ancient books of the Shouyi Museum	Ancient books	Title Index	History, Literature	About 15000	None	None
97	Central University of Finance and Economics Library	None						
98	Central University for Nationalities Library	Central University for Nationalities Ancient Books Resource Library	Ancient resources	Full-Text image	History, Literature	About 1000	None	None
99	Chongqing University Library	Chongqing University Featured Resource Library	Academic Thematic Database, Three Gorges Digital Library, Image Resource Library		History, Human Geography		None	None
100	Nanjing University of Science and Technology Library	None						